

**Polymeric Complexes of 2-Mercapto-
carboxylic Acids with Nickel(II)**

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THE complexes of 2-mercaptopropionic acid with different metal ions have been studied extensively¹.

Study on other similar type of 2-mercaptocarboxylic acids with different transition metal ions has not been carried out. The complexes of SH containing ligands have a great interest because of the controversy on the nature of complexation of SH group with metal. The present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of Ni^{II} polymeric complexes with 2-mercaptocarboxylic acids

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and their pyridine derivatives. The acids are, 2-mercaptovaleric (HMV), 2-mercaptocaproic (HMC), 2-mercaptoheptanoic (HMH) and 2-mercaptooctanoic (HMO) acids.

Experimental

All the 2-mercapto acids were prepared by the known procedure². Purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. Nickel chloride and nitrate used were of AnalaR grade. Equimolar amounts of the metal salt solution in water and the ligand solution in methanol were mixed and stirred continuously at room temperature till a dark green solid was obtained. It was filtered and washed with hot distilled water to remove excess of metal solution and then washed with acetone to remove the unreacted ligand, if any. The complexes of 2-mercaptoheptanoic and 2-mercaptooctanoic acids were recrystallised from chloroform. The base derivatives were prepared by dissolving above complexes in pyridine. This mixture was heated on an oil-bath at 110° till almost dry and the last traces of pyridine were pumped out in vacuum.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by using the Gouy method at room temperature. The molecular weight measurements were done by Rast method using biphenyl as a solvent (m.p. 71°). Infrared spectra of ligands (neat) and the complexes (KBr pellet) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The complexes were dark-green solid, insoluble in water and common organic solvents. They however, showed a gradation in solubility in chloroform and DMF. The complexes of HMV and HMC are insoluble even in hot chloroform, those of HMH and HMO were soluble in hot and cold chloroform respectively.

The elemental analyses (Table 1) showed the composition (NiLX.H₂O) and for base adducts (NiLXB); where L=HMV or HMC or HMH or HMO; X=Cl⁻ or NO₃⁻ and B=pyridine. The complexes were non-electrolytes in CHCl₃ and DMF. The molecular weight measurements gave large values in the range of 7 000–11 000 for the complexes of HMH and HMO. The molecular weight for the other complexes of HMV and HMC were not carried out because they were all insoluble even in biphenyl. It is suggested that these complexes may be polymeric in nature including base adducts. Thermal studies (TG and DTA) of all the complexes, except base adducts, show one endothermic and two exothermic peaks in air at 135, 225 and 525° respectively, whereas the base adducts show two exothermic peaks and the absence of endothermic peak. The endothermic peak at 135° in all non-base complexes suggests the presence of water molecule. All the non-base and base adduct complexes are stable up to 105 and 160° respectively. Above this temperature, breakdown of the complex begins and stable residue is

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)						Mol. Wt.	μ_{eff} B.M.
	Ni	Cl	S	C	H	N		
Ni(MV)ClH ₂ O	23.62 (23.93)	14.23 (14.45)	13.00 (13.07)	24.01 (24.46)	4.05 (4.48)	—	—	2.46
Ni(MC)ClH ₂ O	22.15 (22.64)	13.24 (13.67)	12.00 (12.34)	23.18 (27.77)	4.82 (5.01)	—	—	2.47
Ni(MH)ClH ₂ O	21.32 (21.48)	12.81 (12.97)	11.02 (11.71)	30.65 (30.73)	5.09 (5.92)	—	~10 000	3.01
Ni(MO)ClH ₂ O	19.86 (20.43)	12.23 (12.34)	11.00 (11.14)	33.21 (33.42)	5.63 (5.92)	—	~7 000	3.02
Ni(MV)NO ₃ H ₂ O	21.42 (21.59)	—	11.13 (11.77)	21.00 (22.0)	3.23 (4.05)	4.81 (5.15)	—	2.60
Ni(MC)NO ₃ H ₂ O	20.17 (20.53)	—	11.03 (11.19)	24.03 (25.19)	4.15 (4.55)	4.11 (4.89)	—	2.64
Ni(MH)NO ₃ H ₂ O	18.89 (19.57)	—	10.15 (10.67)	27.12 (28.01)	4.31 (5.00)	4.09 (4.67)	~11 000	3.00
Ni(MO)NO ₃ H ₂ O	18.56 (18.70)	—	9.44 (10.19)	30.11 (30.59)	4.80 (5.42)	4.17 (4.46)	~9 000	3.01
Ni(MV)Cl py	19.00 (19.16)	11.26 (11.57)	10.25 (10.46)	38.01 (39.19)	4.43 (4.57)	4.32 (4.55)	—	2.68
Ni(MH)Cl py	18.18 (18.33)	11.02 (11.17)	9.86 (10.01)	40.12 (41.21)	4.63 (4.99)	4.11 (4.37)	—	2.70
Ni(MH)Cl py	17.23 (17.56)	10.11 (10.60)	9.37 (9.59)	41.78 (43.67)	5.00 (5.38)	4.01 (4.18)	~11 000	3.02
Ni(MO)Cl py	16.43 (16.85)	9.56 (10.17)	8.86 (9.20)	44.66 (45.74)	5.54 (5.74)	3.62 (4.02)	~8 000	3.02
Ni(MV)NO ₃ py	17.23 (17.32)	—	9.24 (9.61)	35.85 (36.05)	4.00 (4.20)	8.21 (8.41)	—	2.72
Ni(MC)NO ₃ py	16.32 (16.92)	—	8.86 (9.22)	37.24 (38.06)	3.82 (4.61)	7.75 (8.07)	—	2.78
Ni(MH)NO ₃ py	16.14 (16.26)	—	8.44 (8.86)	40.03 (40.46)	4.01 (4.98)	7.24 (7.76)	~11 000	3.00
Ni(MO)NO ₃ py	15.47 (15.66)	—	8.25 (8.53)	41.83 (42.15)	4.91 (5.33)	7.11 (7.47)	~10 000	3.02

formed at about 600°. The residue from TGA agree with the composition of the complexes derived on the basis of elemental analysis.

The magnetic moments of all the polymers are in the range of 2.46–3.02 B.M. which were slightly lower than the spin-only value (3.18 B.M.) for octahedral Ni^{II} complexes³. The low values may be due to metal-metal interaction⁴. In the electronic spectra of all polymer complexes, three weak bands were observed at 8 800–9 800, 16 000–17 700 and 23 250–25 400 cm⁻¹ attributed to ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂) and ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions respectively under an octahedral environment around Ni^{II} ion⁵. The octahedral geometry of these complexes is further supported by ν₂/ν₁ ratio, which is around 1.8. The lower value of ν₂/ν₁ ratio compared to octahedral aquo-complexes may be due to the asymmetric environment around Ni^{II} (Ref. 6).

The ligand field parameters like 10Dq, B, β and ligand field stabilisation energy (LFSE) have been calculated for all complexes⁷. The calculated 10Dq values of all the complexes suggest that the ligand may be placed between water and ammonia in the spectrochemical series. The B-values are lower than the free-ion values indicating the orbital overlap and delocalisation of d-orbitals. The β-values obtained are less than one suggesting a considerable amount of covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds⁸.

Ir spectra of all the polymeric Ni^{II} complexes, show a characteristic band for SH stretch at 2 490 cm⁻¹, which shifted from 2 550 cm⁻¹ of the ligand spectrum. This indicates that the sulphur of SH group is taking part in complex formation without getting deprotonated. The broad OH stretching band found in the ligands at 3 300–2 700 cm⁻¹ was not observed in the polymeric complexes, indicating the deprotonation of the OH group. The C–S stretching frequency in all the complexes is observed at 635 cm⁻¹ while it is found at 720 cm⁻¹ in the ligands. The two bands due to symmetric and antisymmetric COO⁻ vibrations which appeared in the ir spectra of the ligand at 1 420 and 1 610 cm⁻¹ respectively also shifted to 1 390 and 1 585 cm⁻¹. From this it appears that all the mercapto-acids are behaving as monobasic bidentate ligands in which SH is not deprotonated. The new bands appearing at 430 and 320 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes are ascribed to Ni–O and Ni–S vibrations respectively. Ni–Cl bands were not observed upto 250 cm⁻¹ in these polymer compounds, the bridging M–Cl frequencies have been shown to occur below 250 cm⁻¹ (Ref. 8). Hence, it is concluded that chloride acts as a bridging centre between the two nickel atoms.

In the nitrate complexes the presence of spectral bands at 1 270s, ~1 485s, ~970s, ~820m, 710w and 745w cm⁻¹ suggests⁹ that NO₃ groups behave as bidentate and bridging centres. The bands at 3 600–3 200, 1 630–1 600 and 735 cm⁻¹ in all the polymer complexes indicate the presence of water molecule coordinated to the metal¹⁰. The bands at

625 and 490–495 cm⁻¹ in all the base adducts suggest that the nitrogen of pyridine is coordinated to the metal atom¹¹.

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